

Border-as-Flesh: Towards a Theory of Border Reversibility

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Abstract: This article theorizes the inability of state borders to implement the forms of separation they aim and claim to enact. To do so, it examines the geopolitical consequences of this failure by thinking the state border through a body of literature that critiques the notion of the body as a border between self and world. In particular, the article draws on Maurice Merleau-Ponty's articulation of the "flesh" to examine how the state border "intertwines" subjects and objects, allowing for their "reversibility." The article argues that the border-as-flesh opens space for sketching a theory of border reversibility that can help us imagine an alternative politics that seeks to dissolve the border's repressive political functions.

Keywords: Borders; Merleau-Ponty; border security; body; self

The separation of one thing from another has always been central to the concept of the political, despite liberal appeals to a universal humanity. Borders are often the mechanism through which the politics of separation is both imagined and managed. We do not need to look too far to see such a politics at play, or to see a border facilitate and accelerate a regressive politics of separation. Wall-builders, anti-immigrant demagogues, and ethno-nationalists are all having their day across the globe. For this politics, the state border has come to encapsulate an imagined counter-revolutionary project against the spatial and social dislocations of globalization in an age of "waning sovereignty."² We are told that these borders must be stronger, bigger, longer, and ubiquitous, even though state borders have never been more heavily policed, or that millions of people have been detained and deported from the rich countries of the Global North over the last four decades.³ The world we are called to sustain is one of separations, one that depends as much on what it excludes as it includes.

Achille Mbembe has a word for this political logic: "borderization." This term describes how "world powers permanently transform certain spaces into impassable places for certain classes of populations."⁴ Mbembe argues that borderization creates "dead spaces of non-connection which deny the very idea

of a shared humanity, of a planet, the only one we have, that we share together, and to which we are linked by the ephemerality of our common condition.”⁵ Borderization is a creative process, one in which space is continually transformed to enforce regimes of separation threatened by the mobility and circulation of certain people and things. But, as Mbembe also notes, “every feasible means is put to work to impose a regime of separation whose functioning paradoxically depends on a proximate intimacy with those who have been separated.”⁶ Borders always keeps in dialogue, however faintly, the worlds that they separate, otherwise the political effects of separation would cease to have any meaning. And once a political separation is established, new modes of separation can be imagined and developed once more.

The intertwined relationship between what the border supposedly separates was obvious to me—although not in a theoretically sophisticated way—growing up in Northern Ireland during and beyond the last decade of the Troubles. During the Troubles, the border between Northern Ireland and the Republic of Ireland was heavily policed and surveilled, with large watchtowers and heavily armed soldiers guarding major entry points by road. Often, small roads between the two states were blocked entirely. Moving between Northern Ireland and the Republic of Ireland was a clearly discernible event—it was impossible not to notice a separation between one place and another. Cathal McCall notes how the border was central to Irish identities in this period, where “[f]or Irish nationals, the border was the scar through the indivisible island and a barrier of their national home place. For the Ulster British, the border became an existential border—the last line of defense—that maintained their identity, position, and privilege.”⁷ The border thus operated to keep these identities separated, even if nationalists and unionists might each live on different sides of that border.

In the decades after 1998’s Good Friday Agreement, however, the Irish border has become characterized by what Katy Hayward calls its “insignificance” as “one of the most seamless and frictionless borders in the world.”⁸ Crossing the border is no longer an event. The separation between the two states is not clearly demarcated. Road signs change; speed limits shift from miles to kilometers; pound sterling exchanges for Euro. But these are largely superficial changes compared to the pre-1998 border. Instead of a clear separation between two distinct places, the border accentuates a continuity between them. As McCall writes, “The Irish borderscape has been such a liberating space for intercultural contact, communication and cooperation that has interrogated binary distinctions between Irish nationalists and Ulster British unionists and has envisioned the border as a peace project.”⁹ After years of political maneuvering and compromise, the border does not collapse the two separate states into one state, but instead allows for a relationality to develop between the two places, where “moving, trading and working across the [Irish] border ha[s] become both easy and unremarkable.”¹⁰ There remains a Republic of Ireland and a Northern Ireland, but they are defined less by their separation than their

interconnectedness. Such relationality seemed unthinkable in the final decades of the twentieth century.

Of course, the transformation of the Irish border does not mean that all the previous political problems have disappeared from the island. Such a conclusion would be absurd. It would also be naïve to think that the Good Friday Agreement and the transformation of the Irish border were not also immersed in flows of global capital and the construction of new modes of extraction and exploitation. Whereas the direct violence of the Troubles ended, the peace process in Northern Ireland brought about other forms of violence, even if they were more structural and less direct: Peace also meant welfare reform, privatization, and austerity.¹¹ It enabled the UK, by way of Tony Blair's Labour government, to transform a region that had remained mostly immune to the Thatcherite neoliberal revolution. The borders between social classes have been redrawn as the geopolitical border disappears.

Brexit has also thrown the post-1998 Irish border into question, returning the border to the Irish political imagination in a way that threatens the forms of relationality that developed in the aftermath of the Good Friday Agreement.¹² At the same time, a growing anti-immigrant politics has emerged in both states in the twenty-first century. In Northern Ireland, the major Unionist party—the Democratic Unionist Party—continues to espouse rhetoric about the dangers of illegal immigration, a rhetoric they employed effectively during and since the Brexit referendum.¹³ In the Republic of Ireland, the slogan “Ireland is full” has echoed around increasingly violent anti-immigrant riots and marches in various parts of the country, including the burning of a hotel housing asylum seekers.¹⁴ A new, double-edged border has thus entered the political imagination in Ireland, one that pertains not only to the internal but to the external boundaries of the island, and one that risks instilling the kinds of sharp separations that once characterized the border between the north and south of the island.

But this transformation of the geopolitical border from a hardened, militarized zone to a barely perceptible crossing does at least point toward a different imaginary of the border, one that allows for new political formulations to emerge—for example, the envisaging and potential construction of a united Ireland, a possibility reflected in the success of the Republican and democratic socialist party Sinn Féin in recent elections on both sides of the border, although support for Sinn Féin decreased in the 2024 Irish General Election, mainly due to the party's ambiguous response to the anti-immigration protests. This example also reveals two fundamental but often contradictory truths about state borders. On the one hand, state borders can enforce regimes of separation between territories and people, which shore up the rights of one group of people at the expense of another group of people. In broad terms, regimes of separation play out in the Global North's shutting of its borders to the Global South, as is evident with the US-Mexico border, the EU's Fortress Europe policy, or Australia's offshore detention regime, even though these borders are also highly flexible and porous to certain migrants. Regional border dynamics—like those in Ireland, or

India and Pakistan—also reveal regimes of separation that prioritize one group over another. On the other hand, these state borders always fail, in an ultimate sense, in enacting separation as these borders cannot engender a complete split between the separated territories and people because the supposedly separated territories and people can never be fully autonomous. They are ontologically dependent on one another, as I will later show.

My aim in this article is to understand the geopolitical consequences of border's inability to enact complete separation by thinking it through a body of literature that critiques the notion of the body as a border between self and world. In particular, I draw on Maurice Merleau-Ponty's articulation of "the flesh" to examine how the border brings into existence opposing political subjectivities, not because of the border's separation of subject and object, but its intertwining, to borrow Merleau-Ponty's terminology, of subject and object. In the case of geopolitical borders, the identification of subject and object is not always clear-cut, nor easily mapped onto specific concrete situations. However, it is clear that when it comes to border struggles, some groups are marked as less worthy subjects, and they are objectified in the process—or at the very least, they are classified in restrictive, racialized, and criminalized ways that undermine their status as subjects. For the sake of this paper, therefore, I find the subject/object analogy helpful theoretically, while also recognizing its limits and the need to be cautious in applying it to concrete situations.

The flesh, I suggest, enables us to better understand the intertwined relationship between subjects and objects at and through borders. For Merleau-Ponty, the flesh is a "general thing," something that exists at all levels of ontology. Likewise, the border is also omnipresent on a political and social level, as it is not simply restricted to demarcating between one territory and another, but also undergirds lived experience inside and outside state borders in a variety of ways. Crucially, for Merleau-Ponty, the flesh is characterized by reversibility, where the subject passes into the realm of the object and vice versa. It is my claim here that contemporary manifestations of state borders often attempt to negate this reversibility through the articulation of clear and distinct subjects and objects or demarcations of territory and non-territory.

The article initially discusses the key tenets of Merleau-Ponty's articulation of the flesh. Then, with the help of Judith Butler, I think through the relationality of the flesh and its challenge to liberal conceptions of the relationship between self and the other. From here, I consider how contemporary political manifestations of the border often work against the flesh, seeking to deny any relationality between the realities that the border attempts to separate. The relationship between security and vulnerability is fundamental to the border's workings against the flesh, but this relationship, I suggest, can also be key to reframing the border-as-flesh as a hinge that facilitates peaceful and non-violent reversibility. Through this reframing, I finish the article by developing the early foundations for a theory of border reversibility, which sees the border-as-flesh

as an imaginary that can help us formulate political and social alternatives to the violent, exclusionary, and exploitative role of the border today.

I should note here that the examples of border politics and practices that I theorize and critique are extreme and usually oppressive situations, such as detention, displacement, and deportation. Doing so, however, does not overlook the fact that lots of people traverse borders on a daily basis as tourists, guest or temporary workers, or even as undocumented migrants. Likewise, for others, borders impose new social and political limits when, for example, new states are formed or special economic zones are established.¹⁵ The border is not a single and easily definable entity and the experience of crossing it may radically differ for different social, economic, and racial groups, and at times also differ randomly. It is thus a site and method that keeps open multiplicities and contradictions, and my focus here on one articulation of borders highlights the logic of separation always at their foundation. This focus allows me to show that even in these most separatist materializations of the border logic, separations are bound to fail, and the connectedness of the two sides always manifests itself in some shape or form.

BORDER-AS-FLESH

My broad claim in this article is that the border as a political entity cannot undo the intertwinement of subject and object, even when the most extreme forms of separation are imagined and executed by nation-states in their use of borders. Merleau-Ponty's concept of the flesh enables us to theorize this claim. By constructing the border-as-flesh, my approach here is in conversation with a vast body of literature and theory on borders that seeks to understand how borders keep in dialogue the things that they supposedly separate. Much work on the ontology of borders, alongside theories of deterritorialization, has attempted in different ways to understand the intertwined relationship between the inside and outside of borders, illustrating how borders function within and beyond the geographical regions of nation-states.¹⁶ Likewise, literature in critical globalization studies, history, political theory, geography, and anthropology has also wrestled with the contradictory nature of state borders, exemplifying that the modern state form depends as much on restricting mobility—even within its territories—as it does on facilitating movement within and beyond the nation-state.¹⁷ In many ways, my argument is informed by Sandro Mezzadra and Brett Neilson's concept of "border as method," which seeks to move beyond the border as an "object" of analysis to instead consider the border as what they call an "epistemological device, which is at work whenever a distinction between subject and object is established."¹⁸ The border here ceases merely to be an "object" at hand, but instead becomes an active process bringing subjects and objects into being and sustaining social relationships.

In a similar vein to Mezzadra and Neilson, Harsha Walia explores the productive power of the border through her theory of “border imperialism.” She likewise challenges the understanding of borders as “fixed or static lines,” instead pushing us to see borders as “productive regimes concurrently generated by and producing social relations of domination.”¹⁹ As “productive regimes,” borders become central to facilitating the dispossession of communities and capturing of land for capitalist extraction and interests, as well as securitizing the benefits and profits of this dispossession. Acts of colonization and capitalist extraction on the part of Western nation-states and companies displace (often Indigenous) communities from their lands, forcing them to migrate, where they are met with “the simultaneous fortification of the border—often by those very same Western powers that are complicit in these displacements—which renders the migration of displaced people as perilous.”²⁰ This simultaneity is not a contradiction; it is the border working to shield and enhance hegemonic power.

My use of the “flesh” has commonalities with Didier Bigo’s metaphor of the Möbius ribbon—a band or loop with a twist that creates a non-orientable surface in which clockwise and anti-clockwise cannot be distinguished—which Bigo uses to think through the relationship between internal (societal) and external (national) security at state borders.²¹ Resting on a Foucauldian reading of governmentality, Bigo argues that “the identity of what is security is in a process of externalization of the inside and the internalization of the outside” and thus “the boundaries of security... don’t know where the inside ends and where the outside begins.” The border becomes a means of managing this confused relationship, where in “making the territorial border

the border of the identities [of security],” society is “protected outside as well as inside through a strategy of maximum security.”²² As Bigo implies, insides and outsides are deeply implicated in one another. Any attempt to think about them separately is destined to fail. I seek to build upon Bigo’s theory by drawing on Merleau-Ponty’s theory of the flesh to move toward a theory of reversibility that can work to undermine a regressive logic of security.

The border thus might separate things and people from one another, but it only does so because these things and people are already intertwined in the same phenomenal reality. In other words, the border separates things and people precisely because they are already intertwined rather than preventing them from becoming inter-twined. When we think with Merleau-Ponty’s concept of “the flesh,” we see that the politics of the border will always fail to maintain the separation between inside and outside. Such politics must fail since, as Merleau-Ponty explains, subject-object relations are never stable but are always vulnerable to each other, much like the subjects and objects that appear in the geopolitical field, as I outlined above.

Of course, even if borders fail to enact complete separation, they still have political and material consequences for those who encounter state borders, and

the failure does not stop nation-states from attempting to enact more extreme systems of separation. Where the Irish example might show how the border-as-flesh works to facilitate a political relationality that brings about peace, there are countless examples of how breaking down a state border can lead to further violence and seemingly erase the possibility of peace. We can think here of military invasions, such as Russia's invasion of Ukraine, and its earlier annexation of Crimea, but also US military incursions into Afghanistan and Iraq earlier in the century. What we touch on with these contrasting examples, therefore, is that when the border-as-flesh is exposed by political actions on, around, and through borders, a whole host of more or less violent possibilities emerge.

As a political entity, the border often works against the intertwinement of subject and object. As Anne McNiven argues, “[b]order policing is the spatial work through which the distinction between citizens and aliens is ordered and policed. It involves the discursive framing and material management of spaces through which we come to recognize our political relation to others.”²³ Such discursive framing is not an effect of a static border, but a border that is both spatially and temporally mobile. Hagar Kotef and Merav Amir, for example, name what they call “the imaginary line” employed by the Israeli military throughout the West Bank, where soldiers set up checkpoints by drawing an imaginary line that delimits the movement of Palestinians within the territory.²⁴ But since the lines are imaginary, and knowledge of that imaginary is controlled by the soldiers, then the lines are likely to be transgressed, and thus “the operation of discipline is set up to fail.”²⁵ We can see here how the failure of the border to realize its political intentions is sometimes the point. The operational capacity of borders can be designed in such a way to deliberately enhance this failure, using the intertwining of both sides of the border to punish one group over another.

FLESH, OTHER, BORDER

In order to construct the border-as-flesh, we need to understand Merleau-Ponty's initial intention for the concept. He introduces “the flesh” in an essay called “The Intertwining—The Chiasm,” published in *The Visible and The Invisible*, a book that was incomplete at his death in 1961.²⁶ The flesh is by no means any easy concept to define. Is it a substance, even if imperceptible? Is it merely an abstraction, a way of understanding our interactions in the world? It is not, Merleau-Ponty tells us, “matter”; “the visible”; or “a representation of the mind.” Instead, he calls it “a general thing, midway between the spatiotemporal individual and the idea, a sort of incarnate principle that brings a style of being wherever there is a fragment of being.” He compares it more to an “element,” in the classical sense, such as “water, air, earth, and fire.” The flesh, he argues, brings an “‘element’ of Being.”²⁷

David Macauley notes that Merleau-Ponty's engagement with the classical elements to explain his theory of the flesh is not merely in passing, but draws heavily on Ancient Greek theories of perception, especially the ideas of Plato

and Aristotle, where “bodies cannot act or be acted upon unless they are in contact with one another—literally in-touch.”²⁸ The flesh thus encapsulates Merleau-Ponty’s attempt to overcome the enduring legacies of Cartesian philosophy’s dualism, with its sharp borders between mind and matter—what Merleau-Ponty describes as “bifurcation of subject and object.”²⁹ Instead, Merleau-Ponty’s thought is characterized by “the fact that we discover ourselves as embodied creatures living in the midst of a changing world. One’s self is not narrowly delimited by the boundaries of one’s skin but is spread over a region ... that extends into the ambient environment as far as one’s concerns stretch.”³⁰ The flesh, in this sense, undergirds a world in which every thing, including the environment, is interdependent. This world is not beyond corporeal borders, because each living thing still retains a distinctiveness within the flesh (otherwise they would simply collapse into the same), but it is a world where such borders are structured by their relationality—as they serve to intertwine subject and object—rather than by their capacity to separate.

Through the flesh, Merleau-Ponty describes the simultaneous subjective and objective dimensions of the lived body; how the body can both be the seer and the seen, the touching and the touched, in the same moment without the subject and object being reduced to the same. How is it, Merleau-Ponty contemplates, that the lived body has “double belongingness to the order of the ‘object’ and to the order of the ‘subject’”?³¹ The flesh is the “hinge,” to use another of Merleau-Ponty’s terms, that ensures this “double belongingness”; it is what binds subject and object together but retains their distance. To exemplify this point, Merleau-Ponty discusses the phenomenon of a hand touching the other hand, in which the touching hand—which we think belongs exclusively to the subjective domain—opens a tactile world of which the touching hand is also a part; it joins what Merleau-Ponty describes as the “rank of the touched.”³² “Through this crisscrossing within it of the touching and the tangible,” writes Merleau-Ponty, “its own movements incorporate themselves into the universe they interrogate, are recorded on the same map as it.”³³ At once, then, the subject, which touches in order to understand, is implicated in the world that it touches, because the subject can also be touched in the same moment; it is an object in the world it seeks to understand.

Reversibility is central to understanding the flesh. In the same way that the touching hand can never reach pure coincidence with the hand touched, or the seer with the seen, the subject and object can never reach unity without one being reversed into the other, without one passing from the domain of touching or seeing to the domain of the touched or seen, and vice versa. Reversibility here does not mean that subjects and objects are simply affected by one another; instead it insists that they are ontologically interdependent—that their very existence is intertwined in the other.³⁴ With the flesh, Merleau-Ponty argues for a way to maintain “distance at the same time as connection,” so that subject and object are simultaneously distinct and ontologically intertwined.³⁵

Reversibility is the process that maintains this connection without the collapse of subject and object into the same.

The concept of the flesh not only has implications for our understanding of perception, but also for the ways in which we conceive of our encounters with other lived bodies. As Merleau-Ponty asks, “why would this generality, which constitutes the unity of my body, not open it to other bodies? The handshake too is reversible; I can feel myself touched as well and at the same time as touching.”³⁶ This reversibility between self and other is a theme that Merleau-Ponty began developing before his articulation of the flesh. In course notes from his lectures at the Collège de France in the mid-1950s, collected in the book *Institution and Passivity*, Merleau-Ponty argues that “there is no reception of the other person, nor perception, which reaches the other; it would be necessary to be the other.”³⁷ We never reach pure coincidence; I can never see how the other sees me and vice versa. But, crucially for Merleau-Ponty, there is no reception of the self that is not also caught up in others. He writes: “We do not make contact with ourselves any more than we make contact with others. Thus, no absolute privilege of the I. [A] world with several compossible entrances. We are one for the others. Me-others hinge, which is common life, like me-my body hinge, which for me is not just weight, a curse, but also my flywheel.”³⁸ While there is no moment of coincidence, there is also no moment of complete separation. Our subjectivity is always in correspondence, always “coiling over,” with our objectivity.

Judith Butler takes up this version of relationality in their recent phenomenological exploration of the COVID-19 pandemic. The pandemic showed, they note, that we do not simply share a world with other distinct beings, but that we impinge upon others; what is inside our bodies (our breath, for example) can be inside another body and cause that body harm, and vice versa. “To be a body at all,” Butler writes, “is to be bound with others and with objects, with surface, and the elements, including the air that is breathed in and out, air that belongs to no one and everyone.”³⁹ We are simultaneously living outside and within one another. “I am not fully sealed as a bounded creature,” Butler concludes, “but emit breath into a shared world where I take in air that has been circulating through the lungs of others.”⁴⁰ The pandemic, in other words, revealed the workings of the flesh. The body is not a shield; an entity that excludes, even if it wants to. We are implicated in one another whether we like it or not.

The pandemic might have revealed the ontology of the flesh, but this does not mean that all individuals, organizations, and state actors accept the social and political consequences of this ontology. For one, the flesh works against the key assumptions of the self-enclosed liberal individual and, more importantly in today’s context, against the liberal individual’s offspring, the atomized and competitive neoliberal individual. Butler makes the point that “individuality is an imagined status and depends on specifically social forms of the imaginary.”⁴¹ The pandemic might have exposed the limitations of this social imaginary; it

might have revealed that we are irrevocably interconnected; but this imaginary is so deeply embedded in Western culture and (neo)liberal societies that even when it is exposed as problematic, any alternative imaginary struggles to breathe.

The flesh, therefore, is not merely a challenge to dominant Western ontologies of the relationship between humans and the environment, or self and other. The flesh also has “both ethical and political consequences for our times, for it offers a way of understanding interdependency that moves beyond the ontology of isolated individuals encased in discrete bodies.”⁴² Where Butler explores these ethical and political consequences in the context of the pandemic, I want to examine them in relation to state borders. If we think through this ontology in the context of borders, we can see that the subject that seeks to repel an object from a given territory using the border is not extricating itself from that object as it often imagines. Instead, the border ensures that the subject becomes implicated in the life of that other, and vice versa. We might say that the subject and object are constituting one another— the white citizen, for example, might seek to distinguish itself from the racialized migrant by drawing a hard border and preventing any kind of reversibility. Political and legal structures often prevent such a reversal from happening in practice, but they also make such reversal contingent, as is made manifest by changes in citizenship rules and immigration policy. The possibility of such a reversal can never be fully extinguished because if the political and legal determines what can and cannot be reversed, then all it takes is alternative articulations of political and legal structures to transform the relations of reversibility. The Irish example above proves that relations of reversibility can change. The ontological reversibility of the border-as-flesh thus under- pins political forms of reversibility, which seek to manage reversibility without being able to fully extinguish its possibility.

THE BORDER AGAINST THE FLESH

Before we move towards a theory of border reversibility, let us start by thinking about how the border as a political entity works against the flesh, because this is, in some ways, the simpler scenario. Deportation and detention are perhaps the most obvious examples. Nicholas De Genova observes “the functionality of deportation in our contemporary sociopolitical scene for enacting in a very blunt and deeply consequential way the divide between the ‘inside’ and ‘outside’ of the space of the state.”⁴³ It is also important to note that this divide occurs not only in geographical space—where migrants are placed outside the geography of the nation-state—but also in social spaces within the nation-state. De Genova writes that “the most productive power of deportation operates for the great majority of people who are susceptible to deportation but who do not get deported. This is how deportation contributes to the precarisation of migrants.”⁴⁴ In this scenario, deportation looms as a shadow over the lives of the most precarious migrants, a perpetual and potentially imminent disciplinary power that maintains a separation between them and secure citizens.⁴⁵

Deportation is thus an effective way for the power of the border as a political entity, manifested as the state border, to work against the fundamental ontological relationality of the flesh and to instill the kinds of separation that allow for global social divisions that maintain hierarchies and systems of domination.

Alongside deportation, detention reconfigures the border as a prison.⁴⁶ On some occasions, this prison is literally on the state border, where migrants are held in detention centers. On other occasions, migrants are stopped at the border and imprisoned within the nation state. But as is increasingly the case, the border-as-prison can often be far outside the territory of the geographical border that migrants seek to cross. This is most obvious in the offshoring of migrant detention, especially on remote islands, a policy favored by governments across the Global North in recent years. Moreover, as Alison Mountz notes in her work on offshore migrant detention—what she calls the “enforcement archipelago”—the island detention center becomes an island within the geographical island, so that the spatial form of the island becomes replicated in the method of detention.⁴⁷ The island, in other words, is both a physical location of detention and an imaginary for the specific form of detention. The border becomes not merely about the separation but also the enclosure of subjects and objects in different imaginary (and often real) islands.

Offshoring is interlinked with outsourcing. The EU, for example, has been outsourcing migrant detention to countries in Eastern Europe, Africa and West Asia for decades, funding the construction of detention centers, training local populations in prison enforcement, and even providing aid and development grants and relaxing visa restrictions for nationals from the countries housing these prisons.⁴⁸ In April 2022, the UK government announced a five-year trial to outsource the detention and processing of asylum seekers to Rwanda, effectively paying the Rwandan government to problem-solve the UK’s asylum policies, although after extended legal injunctions, it was eventually cancelled.⁴⁹ The US has historically outsourced some of its migrant detention to Central and South America and the Caribbean, most famously in the case of Guantanamo Bay.⁵⁰ These forms of outsourcing follow what has become known as the “Australia Model,” replicating the Australian offshore detention regime, where offshore migrant prisons were set up in Manus Island (Papua New Guinea) and Nauru.⁵¹ Despite regular reports of the horrific conditions in these detention centers, widespread physical, mental, and sexual abuse, and countless breaches of international refugee and human rights law, the model has been deemed successful by many countries in the Global North who have sought to replicate it. In 2021, Denmark passed a law to legalize offshore migrant detention. As I write, the UK is loudly promising to “stop the boats,” echoing word-for-word the slogan used by Tony Abbott and his “Operation Sovereign Borders” policy during his successful 2013 Australian election campaign.⁵²

Both offshoring and outsourcing form part of a process that Walia calls “the externalization of borders,” which encompasses “all extraterritorial state

technologies and actions intended to prevent migrants and refugees from reaching the legal jurisdiction of the state.”⁵³ This process of externalization is both defensive, in terms of protecting the interior of a nation-state, but also creative, as it entails repurposing territory outside the nation-state. To this end, offshoring and outsourcing take on the character of “imperial intervention, revealing how the relationship between imperialism and migration is not simply one of cause and effect but, rather, how externalization of migration controls has itself become a method for imperialism in this era.”⁵⁴ Such imperial intervention has enabled “states to erect not only walls but fortresses stretching far beyond the border itself.”⁵⁵ As a result, the border in its political form has the capacity to separate across a wide spatiotemporal terrain, enabling the establishment of distinct subjects and objects in various locales.

The separation of subjects and objects at and through the state border is most obvious in the violence of deportation and detention, but this same separation can also be present in practices that seek to improve and protect the welfare of those on the move and at the margins of nation-states. Serena Parekh argues, for instance, that humanitarianism can often rob asylum seekers and refugees of their lived bodies, in a phenomenological sense, and thus “rather than being political subjects, they become objects of humanitarian aid, bodies to be cared for and protected.”⁵⁶ In this context, the border still works to turn the refugee or asylum seeker into an object, subjected to the humanitarian worker’s gaze and decision-making. The fact that the biggest international humanitarian organizations are based in and governed from the Global North, whose aid recipients are overwhelmingly from the Global South—a problem that many aid workers themselves have pointed out, especially in terms of the devaluing of local knowledge—suggests that the white subject and non-white object that dominate a growing ethno-nationalist politics in the Global North also permeates humanitarianism, albeit in a less overt way. In fact, some scholars have gone as far to argue that humanitarianism constitutes a form of white supremacy, which “veils the racial hierarchies within universalist understandings of the ‘human’.”⁵⁷ Where many see the power of the border to separate as a means to privilege the subject inside the border—or, more precisely, the subject with a secure right to be inside the bordered territory—humanitarianism privileges the object repelled by the border. What this points to is that humanitarianism, no matter how well-intentioned, implicitly accepts an imaginary of the border as a mechanism of separation. And, as Didier Fassin elaborates through his theory of “humanitarian reason,” the relationship between subject and object is asymmetrical, “always directed from above to below, from the powerful to the weaker, the more fragile, the more vulnerable—those who can generally be constituted as victims of an overwhelming fate.”⁵⁸

Discussions around detention, deportation, and humanitarianism foreground a dialectic of security and vulnerability. The vulnerability of the nation-state is managed through the discourse and implementation of security. The vulnerability of the migrant is articulated through the security provided by humanitarianism.

In both scenarios, vulnerability is to be avoided or ameliorated and security becomes the means through which to negate or repair vulnerability.

But, again, this dialectic depends on the border's political capacity to separate subjects and objects: a vulnerable subject (citizen or migrant) in the face of dangerous object (the migrant or border regime). As Bigo notes, the prevalence of security discourse has led, in practical terms, to the "de-differentiation between matters of internal and external security," so that the internal security of the nation-state, for example, is protected by extending the security practices of the state beyond its territorial borders, and the policing of "threats" outside borders becomes the means of ensuring "societal security" inside borders. The irony here is that in defending the border, "agencies of security ... have expanded into a space that no longer respects sovereign boundaries." In other words, by extending beyond borders, these security practices undermine the very world they seek to reinforce. And this move has obvious political and social consequences, because once security inhabits the horizon of the imagination in this way, insecurity, or vulnerability, also appears everywhere. As a result, the blurring of "[i]nternal and external security are embedded in the figure of the 'enemy within,' of the outside inside, which is increasingly labelled with the catchword 'immigrant.'"⁵⁹ Security thus creates the conditions of its own (im)possibility.

SECURITY AND VULNERABILITY

Border security is sustained through regimes of detention and deportation, policy and bureaucratic amendments, and surveillance and biometric technologies, and it is driven by the perceived vulnerability of both the lives and the way of life inside the border.⁶⁰ The border as a political entity, often materialized in the state border, separates the vulnerable subject—which can be perceived as citizens or a way of life—from the dangerous foreign object (often the migrant). Ultimately, however, the vulnerability the secure border seeks to annihilate will always find a way through, not simply because nation-state borders can never be fully secured, but because security and vulnerability are ontologically intertwined.

At the heart of the flesh lies the question of vulnerability, even if Merleau-Ponty does not use the word explicitly. If we think against the flesh and imagine ourselves as isolated individuals, encased in our bodies, radically distinct from others and the world, then we are effectively as vulnerable as we allow ourselves to be. It is a question of how much we intend to let in, both physically and, to a certain extent, psychologically. But we all know this is not really how we experience vulnerability; it is not a tap that we can turn on or off.⁶¹ Instead, it contains an affective register, one outside of our control that emerges through our lived embodiment in, rather than beside or above, the world. The flesh allows us to better understand the phenomenon of vulnerability, because it questions

the body as a border that separates an individual from the world and others. If subject and object are inter-twined instead of separated, reversible instead of immutable, then vulnerability takes on a different dimension. Vulnerability emerges in the relation, within the flesh, rather than against relationality, against the other and the world. Vulnerability becomes a shared condition, and thus one that requires relations of care.

Butler is again helpful here. The idea of vulnerability has animated much of their work over the last two decades, and they return to this theme in their reading of the pandemic, where they link the disavowal of vulnerability to the liberal conceit of individuality. “According to prevailing frameworks of self-interest,” Butler writes, “we act as if our separate lives come first and then we decide on our social arrangements.” But given that our early life is defined by what Butler calls a “primary helplessness” that requires a deep interdependence with others, why do we assume, Butler asks, that we lose this interdependence entirely as we grow older if it is part of our formation as a subject? Butler goes on to argue:

That dependency on others, on provisions, on all that we could not possibly give ourselves, had to be put aside if not fully denied for any of us to decide one day that the one is a singular individual, distinct and spatially closed off from others, not only separated but separate. All individuation is haunted by a dependency that is imagined as if it could be overcome or has already been vanquished.⁶²

Likewise, we might argue that the border as a political entity “is haunted by a dependency that is imagined as if it could be overcome or has already been vanquished,” because it is an illusory shield supposedly protecting the separateness of the vulnerable subject from the dangerous object. But the borders of the body, like the borders of nation-states, are always porous, no matter how hard we attempt to enforce their boundaries. Complete invulnerability is an impossible task, precisely because our vulnerability and security are ontologically intertwined. And yet, the imaginary of the nation-state border as a path towards invulnerability dominates the contemporary political imagination. It does this by separating security from vulnerability, so that security is understood as the absence of vulnerability and vulnerability conceived as the absence of security.

The question here, then, is how do we shift this imaginary? How do we conceptualize the border as a political entity that keeps open the possibility of both security and vulnerability, or that does not see militarized security based on sustained separations as a cure for a vulnerability that cannot be cured? Bigo’s analysis from above may be helpful here, in showing how securitization meant to

address and solve vulnerability only increases it. Or, perhaps to phrase this differently, how do we imagine vulnerability as pathway to security rather than its antithesis? A theory of border reversibility, through imagining the border-as-flesh, is my attempt to begin to answer these questions. Merleau-Ponty's theory of the flesh challenges the idea that we are closed off from the world and one another, that we are isolated bodies that can choose when and where we wish to open our boundaries to others, when and where to be vulnerable. Instead, the flesh insists that our very existence, prior to any kind of consciousness and because we are a lived body, is implicated in the world and with others. The hardened border, whether of the body or the nation-state, is an attempt to disavow this intertwinement, an attempt to see the human or national body as perilous and vulnerable and thus in need of security. It would be naïve to deny the human desire for security, but if we think of the concept of security through the lens of the flesh, we might come to see that security is not achieved by hardening our borders against the world and others, but by strengthening our relational ties with the world and others. In other words, security can be achieved not by denying our vulnerability but by prioritizing it as the primary condition of our interdependence. As in the example of Ireland above, the state border can become a mechanism that facilitates relationality; It can allow a reversibility between security and vulnerability that actually undermines and dissolves violence.

TOWARDS A THEORY OF BORDER REVERSIBILITY

To finish, then, I want to map the early contours of a theory of border reversibility. Part of the impetus for thinking the border-as-flesh is to acknowledge the reality that many people are wedded to the imaginary of the border in its various political manifestations. I agree, in this context, with Butler that “the psychic fear of being without boundaries, fused with others, eradicated in one's distinctness has to be thought through in relation to the desire for boundaries, to shut down openings, to be fully defended or shielded.”⁶³ The desire for borders is rooted in something real, and this is where a politics against borders must start. And this is also where, as Butler also acknowledges in a slightly different context, Merleau-Ponty's concept of “the flesh” can be found wanting when applied to concrete political and social situations. Butler writes: “If we consider Merleau-Ponty's optimistic ‘embrace’ as a way of thinking about the intentional relations to others and the world, it seems clear that it rules out or minimizes the possibility of violence, of erecting borders in the service of defenses, both psychic and political.”⁶⁴ In other words, Merleau-Ponty fails to reckon with the potential defensive movement against the flesh, the desire of the subject to free itself from the object. And even if this is ultimately an impossibility on an ontological level, it does not stop some subjects from trying.

The example of the Irish border is helpful in that it illustrates how the border as a political entity emerges from its ontological foundations. The border can enact a “reciprocal relation,” to use Butler's words, allowing dichotomies like

Northern Irish and Irish to overlap rather than repel one another, and, importantly, for them to be reversible. In many ways, the Irish example exemplifies Audra Simpson's concept of "nested sovereignties," in which sovereign entities can exist within, rather than only outside, other sovereign entities. As Simpson notes in the case of Indigenous political orders, as is also the case in the Irish example, such orders "prevail within and apart from settler governance."⁶⁵ In other words, nested sovereignties signal that the flesh can be both maintained and transformed on a political level simultaneously, from within and without. At the same time, however, the move against the border-as-flesh can have devastating consequences by laying the ground for violence, as is obvious with practices of detention and deportation outlined above, as well as military invasions. The question remains, therefore, of how useful the border-as-flesh might be on a political level if its exposure can lead to vastly contrasting consequences. Prioritizing border reversibility is thus no guarantee of a nonviolent future. In fact, it might open the possibility for increased violence.

For the border-as-flesh to emerge in ways that can bring about rather than prevent nonviolent futures, the asymmetry of border experience—the fact that there is much more at stake for some groups of people than others in border politics—must be prioritized. The border-as-flesh, if it is to enact a peaceful reversibility, requires forms of dispossession, a word Butler uses in conversation with Athena Athanasiou. As Butler acknowledges, "dispossession is precisely what happens when populations lose their land, their citizenship, their means of livelihood, and become subject to military and legal violence. We oppose this ... form of dispossession because it is both forcible and privative." Migrant crises, regimes of deportation and detention, and the differential treatment of citizens and migrants (not to mention the welcoming of tourists) illustrates that these forms of dispossession are much more likely to happen to certain sections of the global population.

Nonetheless, on an ontological level, there are forms of dispossession that we are all vulnerable to, if extremely unevenly. We are beings who can and will be dispossessed, not of our belongings or our identity—although this of course happens in some instances—but dispossessed of our individualism, of our separateness. As Butler argues: "We can only be dispossessed because we are already dispossessed. Our inter-dependency establishes our vulnerability to social forms of deprivation."⁶⁶ In the case of the Irish border, dispossession was a necessary component of the peace process; each side had to lose something that shaped their identities in order to be exposed to the interdependency underpinning their identities in the first place.

A theory of border reversibility rearticulates dispossession, to borrow Simone Drichel's words, as a "fundamentally enabling condition—against the foil of which forms of liberal (and neoliberal) anti-relationality, such as they are associated with the autonomous and self-sufficient subject bequeathed to us by

Enlightenment thought, can only emerge as forms of limitation or deprivation. Because we come into being with and for the other, we are ethically implicated in the lives of others in ways from which we cannot easily extricate ourselves.”⁶⁷ But to become extricated from the supposed security the border engenders is not to fall into forms of irreparable deprivation. This is of course the image presented by anti-immigrant, hardline demagogues, who suggest that the border is the only thing keeping some societies from collapsing into irredeemable disrepair. Instead, to become dispossessed of the security of the border is to recognize the reversibility inherent to all human life, that the forms of deprivation encountered by those on the wrong side of the border are forms of deprivation that we could all experience, even if our political, legal, and social status makes this more unlikely. It is to see that we are who we are because we are ontologically entangled in these forms of deprivation, not because we have managed to completely separate ourselves from such deprivation.

Vulnerability and interdependency are thus not only philosophical or ethical considerations, but also political. There are ways we are all made vulnerable by capitalism as an “institutionalized social order,” for instance, where the economic and social avenues for a livable life are steadily closed and the very ecological conditions of our existence are radically destroyed.⁶⁸ We can resist these forms of vulnerability on a political level without completely disavowing our shared ontological vulnerability.⁶⁹ As Butler puts it, “the task is less a simple affirmation of interdependency than a collective effort to find or forge the best form of interdependency, the one that most closely embodies the ideas of radical equality.”⁷⁰ It is one thing, then, to say that we are interdependent; it is another to build a world in which that interdependence is experienced equally.

Butler notes that the “ethico-political” task facing us “is to establish ... a reciprocal relation that dissolves into neither self-interest nor communitarianism (the alibi for racism), nor national identity (the alibi for border violence and racism).”⁷¹ Border reversibility is a theoretical tool in this ethicopolitical project. State borders are the location—both literal and imaginative—of so many clashes between subjects and objects. They are also the mechanisms that bring into existence two different and often contradictory worlds. But equally, state borders are contested concepts and sites of struggle; their attempts to separate subjects and objects often serve to reveal their ontological interdependence, as is clear in the example of the Irish border, but also in repressive practices of deportation and detention.⁷² By prioritizing the reversibility of the border-as-flesh, we can simultaneously accentuate how the ontology of the border engenders and escalates forms of violence and how such an ontology holds the key to overcoming such violence. It is in this contested space that Merleau-Ponty’s articulation of the flesh can help us theorize and imagine an alternative to regimes of separation enforced through state borders, an alternative enabling us to posit vulnerability as a shared human condition that is distributed vastly unequally. The border-as-flesh, articulated through a theory of border

reversibility, can be the political imaginary for a world order that prioritizes the ontological relationality inherent in the reversibility of state borders; a world where the border collapses rather than entrenches forms of radical inequality.

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